

Product's Structure Representation and Activities Simulation in a Manufacturing System Simulation Framework

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Abstract: - The paper is presenting a set of steps performed for the development of a simulation framework for allocation and routing of some operational resources from a manufacturing system. A representation for the data regarding a product's structure is presented, together with an original algorithm for generating the list of product's components and the list of operations to be performed. There are also presented a set of procedures developed for simulating the supply activities and the arrival of the supplied components into the manufacturing system's warehouse.

Key-Words: - Manufacturing System, Product Structure, Simulation Framework

1 Introduction

Developing a simulation framework for allocation and routing of some operational resources from a manufacturing system involves the establishment of a representation for describing the structure of the products whose manufacturing is simulated.

In [1] it was proposed a Petri Net type representation, starting from individual components which represent inputs in the simulated system (Fig.1) and it is mentioned that, when the simulated manufacturing system is receiving a processing order for a certain product in a specified quantity, the Petri Net which is describing the products structure is covered in reverse order, starting from the product to be manufactured, obtaining the number of initial components to be used for creating the ordered product and creating a list of the operations to be performed.

2 Problem Formulation

The problem approached by the work described in this paper was first to find a suitable data structure, starting from the Petri Net type representation, for storing and processing the data about the products' structure.

Then, the algorithm of covering the Petri Net in reverse order, for obtaining the list of initial components and the list of operations to be performed, had to be defined, implemented and tested.

Once the list of initial components is available, the problem of simulating the supply activities and the arrival of the supplied components was approached.

Also, having defined the list of operations to be performed, some initial steps for preparing the resource allocation and activities scheduling can be defined.

3 Problem Solution

3.1 Building the initial components list and the operations list

The Petri Net presented as an example in [1] could be described using its incidence matrix but, taking into consideration a manufacturing system in which several hundreds of part types are processed, the matrix would have thousands of lines and columns which would make it extremely difficult to use.

Instead of using the incidence matrix, it was preferred to describe the Petri Net using an array, called below the transitions array, in which each element is describing the links of one transition (Fig.2).

An element of the transition array contains a value representing the name of the transition whose links the element is describing and an array, called below the places array, containing data about the places to which the transition is linked.

Fig.1. Petri Net type representation of a product's structure

Transitions Array				
Transition name	Places Array			
T5-3	R5-2	R5-3		
	-1	1	0	0
T6-1	R2-3	R5-3	R6-1	
	-1	-1	1	0
T7-1	R4-2	R6-1	R7-1	R9-2
	-1	-1	1	-1

Fig.2. Transitions array for storing the Petri Net's data

An element of the places array contains the name of one of the places to which the transition is connected and the weight of the corresponding arc.

This representation allows for different places arrays to have different lengths, without the need of filling with null values like in the case of a matrix, thus obtaining a reduction in the size of the necessary memory and in the computing time.

The list of operations to be performed for manufacturing a certain product is built using the transitions array, as follows:

Step 1. A list of components is defined, initially containing only one element: the name of the product to be manufactured. The first position in the components list is defined as the current position;

Step 2. Being "CPE" the element in the current position of the components list, there is searched in the transitions array a transition in whose places array exists an element containing the name of the CPE and a positive arc weight. In other words, there is searched the transition (the operation) whose result is the element in the current position of the components list.

To facilitate the search in Step 2 (to reduce the computing time), the first positions of the places arrays are to be used for the elements having positive arc weights.

Step 3. If the search in Step 2 has no result, the conclusion is that there is no operation to have as its result the element in the current position of the components list, so this element has to be supplied from outside the manufacturing system. In this situation, the value of the current position of the components list is incremented and the algorithm is going back to Step 2;

Step 4. If a result is found during the search in Step 2, then the element from the current position of

the components list is deleted and the algorithm advances to Step 5;

Step 5. From the places array belonging to the element found in the transitions array in Step 2, there are selected the elements with negative arc weights;

Step 6. The names of the places from the elements selected in Step 5 are added to the end of the components list. A place name is added to the end of the list as many times as the absolute value of the negative arc weight;

Step 7. The name of the transition from the element found in the transitions array in Step 2 is added to the beginning of a list of operations to be performed;

Step 8. If the value of the current position is less than or equal to the number of elements in the components list, then the algorithm is going back to Step 2, otherwise the algorithm ends.

The steps performed for applying the above algorithm for manufacturing the R7-1 product are completely described in [2], a Google Docs document created as an annex to this paper.

After applying the algorithm, there were obtained the list of components to be supplied (R8-1, R2-1, R5-1, R2-1, R2-1, R1-1, R3-1) and the list of operations to be performed (T3-2, T1-2, T3-3, T2-2, T2-2, T1-3, T5-2, T2-2, T3-4, T2-3, T2-3, T1-4, T9-1, T5-3, T2-3, T4-1, T9-2, T6-1, T4-2, T7-1).

The algorithm was implemented in a LabVIEW Virtual Instrument (Fig.3) and this was also tested using the example of manufacturing the R7-1 product.

The data from the transitions array was initially manually introduced in a control element on the virtual instrument's front panel. For testing a

Fig.3. LabVIEW algorithm's implementation

method for storing the data in a data file, the data from the control element was first saved into an XML file (Fig.4) and then read from that file for being further processed.

```

<?xml version="1.0" standalone="true"?>
- <LVData xmlns="http://www.ni.com/LVData">
  <Version>11.0</Version>
  - <Array>
    <Name>Transitions array</Name>
    <Dimsize>20</Dimsize>
    - <Cluster>
      <Name>Cluster</Name>
      <NumElts>2</NumElts>
      - <String>
        <Name>Transition name</Name>
        <Val>T1-2</Val>
      </String>
      - <Array>
        <Name>Places Array</Name>
        <Dimsize>2</Dimsize>
        - <Cluster>
          <Name>Cluster</Name>
          <NumElts>2</NumElts>
          - <String>
            <Name>Place name</Name>
            <Val>R1-1</Val>
          </String>
          - <I16>
            <Name>Arc weight</Name>
            <Val>-1</Val>
          </I16>
        </Cluster>
      </Array>
    </Cluster>
  </Array>
</LVData>

```

Fig.4. XML file for storing product’s structure data

The average time for running the virtual instrument for the given data, including writing and reading the XML file, was estimated at 0.15 s.

The list of components to be supplied and the operations list which were obtained after running the LabVIEW implementation were identical to those obtained in [2].

3.2 Activities’ simulation

When the list of components to be supplied is available, some procedures can be developed for simulating the way in which the different components arrive in the manufacturing system.

First of all, because the list of components to be supplied may contain the same component several times, a procedure was developed for merging all the instances of the same component (Fig.5). The procedure is using an well known algorithm for building an array of distinct items, but building in the same time a separate array containing the number of instances of each item of the first array. When a component already exists in the array of distinct items, its corresponding number of instances is incremented.

The procedure outputs an array of clusters, where each cluster contains the name of the component and the number of instances of that component in the product to be manufactured.

When the number of pieces of the product to be manufactured is known, the quantities from each component to be supplied can be determined, multiplying the number of instances of each component by the number of pieces of the product. The procedure developed for this calculus (Fig.6) includes, for simulation purposes, a section for generating a random integer number representing the time needed for supplying a component. The procedure’s output is an array of clusters, where each cluster contains the name of a component, the quantity to be supplied and the time needed for supply. The output array is sorted in ascending order according to the supply time, thus allowing to define the rule that the first component in the array is to be supplied the soonest.

Fig.5. Merging all the instances of the same component

Fig.9. Partially diagram of a simulation virtual instrument

After the quantities to be supplied and the supplying estimated times are computed, the warehouse data is initialized and then the simulator starts an iterative structure.

During each iteration, there is executed the procedure for checking if any batch of components was supplied to the system and, in the positive case, the supplied components are stored in the warehouse.

For each operation from the list of operations to be performed, the corresponding places array is extracted from the transitions array and, for each place in the array, which means for each product representing an input in the activity, the necessary quantity is computed and its availability in the warehouse is checked.

In this way it is determined if, for an operation from the list of operations to be performed, the necessary components for starting the operation are available.

4 Conclusion

The data structure described in this paper proved to be suitable for the main types of processing operations to be applied, especially for the original algorithm designed for building the initial components list and the operations list, and in the same time offered low size files and short computing times.

For moving forward to the stages of resources allocation and tasks scheduling, the data structure will have to include information about the types of working places on which each operation may be performed.

Inside the data describing the ordered product to be manufactured, there will be inserted information about the deadline for delivering the product and also priority information.

Parameters similar to the economic batch quantity will be taken into consideration in simulator's future versions.

If, for the moment, the simulator is intended to start each operation as soon as all the necessary components are available, in future developments the simulator will be able to predict if some ready-to-start operations will have to be delayed for allowing some resources to be allocated to higher priority operations which don't have yet all the necessary starting conditions accomplished.

The simulated system will allow more warehouses and storing places, some of them positioned as input and output areas for some working places.

Transport elements belonging to the manufacturing system will be also simulated, and the necessary durations for the transport activities will be taken into consideration when scheduling the operations and allocating the resources.

References:

- [1] S1. SAVU Tom, Manufacturing System Simulation Framework, Submitted to *IManE 2013 - Innovative Manufacturing Engineering International Conference*, May 23rd, Iasi, Romania.
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